

Deliverable D-JRP22-WP5.4

Workpackage 5

Responsible Partner: ISS

Contributing partners: ANSES, FLI, RIVM, PIWET, NVI, SSI, INIAV, INSA, UT, BIOR, CVRL, IZSS, UNF, UH, IP, LRUJ, NPI, SDAS, COMSATS, VTL

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP22-WP5.4		
Project Acronym	MEME		
Author	Adriano Casulli		
Other contributors	All participants		
Due month of the report	60		
Actual submission month	60		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	Save date: 24 november 2022		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
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	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>		
	EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Other	international	stakeholder(s):
		
	Social Media:		
	Other recipient(s):		

Final Report MEmE

Consortium composition

MEME project coordinator:

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Work packages leaders:

WP1: SAMPLING STRATEGY: J. Karamon (PIWET)

WP2: VALIDATION of PARASITOLOGICAL and MOLECULAR ASSAYS: G. Umhang, F. Boue (ANSES)

WP3: DEVELOPMENT of NEW TOOLS AND PRODUCTION of EPIDEMIOLOGICAL DATA. P. Maksimov (FLI)

WP4: TRAINING, DISSEMINATION and PROFICIENCY TESTING SCHEMES. A. Casulli (ISS)

WP5: SCIENTIFIC and ADMINISTRATIVE MANAGEMENT. A. Casulli (ISS)

Consortium (funded partners):

Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS), Italy (Coordinator); Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut (FLI), Germany; Agence nationale de sécurité sanitaire de l'alimentation, de l'environnement et du travail (ANSES), France; National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), The Netherlands; National Veterinary Research Institute in Pulawy (PIWET), Poland; Norwegian Veterinary Institute (NVI), Norway; Statens Serum Institut (SSI), Denmark; National Institute for Agrarian and Veterinary Research (INIAV), Portugal; Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), Portugal; University of Tartu (UT), Estonia; Veterinary and Food Laboratory (VFL), Estonia; Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment (BIOR), Latvia.

External partners:

Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Sardegna (IZSS), Italy; Department of Agriculture, Food and The Marine (CVRL), Ireland; University of Naples "Federico II" (UNF), Italy; University of Hohenheim (UH), Germany; Institute of Parasitology (IP), Switzerland; Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI), Norway; Svalbard Dyresykehus AS (SDAS), Norway; University Islamabad (COMSATS), Pakistan.

Summary of the work carried out in the Project

MEME is an international multicentre collaborative project that aims to fill research gaps highlighted by international agencies for the detection and control of zoonotic parasites *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (Eg sl), causing alveolar echinococcosis (AE) and cystic echinococcosis (CE), respectively.

MEME achievements were:

- The production of SOPs for the sampling of different matrices from naturally or experimentally infected definitive and intermediate animal hosts.
- The validation of the parasitological (SSCT) and molecular diagnostic (multiplex- and MC-RT-PCR) procedures to detect Em and Eg in different matrices along the food chain.
- The development, validation and comparison of new molecular tools (comparison of DNA extraction and PCRs methods; Novel probe-based real-time PCRs and PCR-RFLPs and multiplex PCR assays).
- Multicentre studies for the production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments: contamination of fresh vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg; prevalence of Em/Eg in dog faeces).
- Quantitative assessment on the impact of human CE in Europe by means of systematic review approach.
- Molecular and clinical epidemiology studies in selected geographical areas.
- Dissemination of project results at different levels (general public, scientific community, experts, health authorities and media).

MEME impacted on animal health, public health and food safety sectors. Beneficiaries of scientific outputs of MEME were EU reference labs, international organizations and all decision makers. **We provided a set of molecular tools, epidemiological risk assessments and quantitative epidemiological models for the detection, surveillance and control of these parasitic infectious diseases in Europe and beyond.**

MEME scientific papers currently published on peer-review journals:

- [Unveiling the incidences and trends of cystic echinococcosis in Europe: a systematic review from the MEME project](#). *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 2022.
- [Cystic echinococcosis in northern Tanzania: a pilot study in Masaai livestock-keeping communities](#). *Parasit Vectors*. 2022.
- [Species and genotypes belonging to *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* complex causing human cystic echinococcosis in Europe \(2000-2021\): a systematic review approach](#). *Parasit Vectors* 2022.
- [Comparison and evaluation of analytic and diagnostic performances of four commercial kits for the detection of antibodies against *E. granulosus* and *multilocularis* in human sera](#). *Comp Immunol Microbiol Infect Dis*. 2022.
- [Insights into Human Cystic Echinococcosis in the Kurdistan Region, Iraq: Characteristics and Molecular Identification of Cysts](#). *Pathogens*. 2022.
- [Chromosome-scale *Echinococcus granulosus* \(genotype G1\) genome reveals the Eg95 gene family and conservation of the EG95-vaccine molecule](#). *Commun Biol*. 2022.
- [A Retrospective Cohort Study on Human Cystic Echinococcosis in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province \(Pakistan\) Based on 16 Years of Hospital Discharge Records](#). *Pathogens*. 2022.
- [Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver](#)

and Bone. Pathogens. 2021.

- New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021–2030. PLoS Negl Trop Dis. 2021.
- Identification of Echinococcus granulosus genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs genotyping assays. Pathogens. 2021.
- Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs (Acinonyx jubatus) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed Besnoitia species. Parasit Vectors. 2021.
- Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for detection of Echinococcus multilocularis in the stool samples of naturally infected red foxes. Animals (Basel). 2020.
- Cystic echinococcosis: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia (Italy). Pathogens. 2020.
- A validated method to identify Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato at species level. Infection, Genetics and Evolution. 2020.
- Bayesian analysis of three methods for diagnosis of cystic echinococcosis in sheep. Pathogens. 2020.
- Species detection within the Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato complex by novel probe-based real-time PCRs. Pathogens. 2020.
- Microsatellite investigations of multiple Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto cysts in single hosts reveal different patterns of infection events between livestock and humans. Pathogens. 2020.
- Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis. The Lancet Global Health. 2020.

Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

Figure 1. Updated PERT chart with interconnections and domino effects between WPs and Tasks of MEME. In red 2 tasks «discontinued» for COVID-19 pandemic and 9 «new» tasks/subtasks implemented in the project.